

Clinical Practice Guideline for Entry Level Nurse Practitioners

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BACKGROUND

- Cosmetic Botox and Facial Filler are temporary treatments to help mitigate the aging process.
- The FDA approved Botox and FF in early 2000s for the treatment of temporarily softening the frown lines between the eyebrows and crows feet in patients 18 to 65 years of age
- In 2015, Americans spent over 13.5 billion dollars on surgical and non-surgical procedures. Cosmetic surgical procedures accounted for 58% and non-invasive cosmetic procedures.
- Currently there is a paucity of literature providing adequate standards for evidence-based practice (EBP)
- Appropriate guidelines are imperative for midlevel practitioner in the aesthetic field.
- The increase of public awareness and acceptance of minimally invasive procedures, such as Botox and FF, increases the size of the consumer market.

DESIGN AND METHOD

- In accordance with the Ace Star Model, a systematic and integrative review was conducted.
- This project only adopted level I, II, III, IV, and V and high and good, quality evidence
- The focus population is nurse practitioner with six months or less experience in injectable administration.
- A minimum of two experts in the field of cosmetic injectables with 2 years or more experience independently evaluated the potential impact of EBP CPG

PURPOSE

- The purpose of this project was to develop guidelines for entry level NPs to competently administer Botox and facial fillers in a medical spa or primary care setting.
- The development of a clinical guideline for non-invasive cosmetic treatments would facilitate accurate formulation and dosage for optimal therapeutic outcomes for every patient
- The desired outcome for this project was to develop clinical guidelines that would improve patient satisfaction, decrease adverse events, and improve NP competency for Botox and FF treatment

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

CLINICAL IMPLICATIONS

- This CPG is the first of any Botox or FF evidence based guidelines for entry-level NPs.
- The findings of the systematic and integrative literature review; and developed CPG and resource tool will help promote quality patient care by assuring safety of patient and individualize treatment plan.

CONCLUSION

- Patient safety and individualized care is imperative when providing aesthetic treatments.
- The lack of evidence based guidelines for novice practitioner in the aesthetic field can result in various complications and poor patient outcomes.
- This quality improvement project has analyzed extensive literature reviews and expert recommendation consensus to develop evidence based guidelines and resources.

